
Learning Activity Worksheet and the Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies of Grade 10- Student in Technology and Livelihood Education

Victoria H. Silva¹, Dr. Dolores D. Versano²

¹Secondary School Teacher II- JHS, ²Part Timer Professor Graduate Studies and Applied Research (GSAR)

¹Callejon National High School, Callejon, San Antonio, Quezon, Philippines

²Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines

ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study is to meet the needs and develop the competencies of the students. It will also help them in preparation for their Senior High School since majority of these students would like to enroll in Technology – Vocational Livelihood Track which also focuses on these entrepreneurial competencies.

The study employed the descriptive research design as it aimed to accurately and systematically describe and identify characteristics, frequencies, trends, and categories of a population, situation or phenomenon. This design was appropriate since it determined and explained the data gathered from the participants' perception towards using Learning activity worksheet.

To analyze the significant difference between mean pretest and posttest scores of the respondents before and after the utilization of Learning Activity Worksheet mean, standard deviation and t-test were used. To examine the significant relationship between student's perception on the use of Learning Activity Worksheet and their personal entrepreneurial skills Pearson-Product Moment Correlation was used.

The hypothesis is not sustained. The null hypothesis stating "there is no significant relationship in student's perception on the use of Learning Activity Worksheet and their personal entrepreneurial skills" is accepted.

Technology and Livelihood Education as one of the subjects offered to secondary students in the Philippines which taught diverse skills promote entrepreneurship education that would develop the personal entrepreneurial competency of the students. With the growing importance of globalization, students must be competitive by enhancing their personal entrepreneurial competencies.

KEYWORDS: Learning Activity Worksheet, Personal entrepreneurial Competencies

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurial competencies are considered a vital piece for aspiring entrepreneurs to pursue entrepreneurial ventures. The Philippine education system has seen radical changes as the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) implemented the K to 12 programs in 2016. To better equip the Filipino students with the needed business skills and competencies, curricular offerings were revised, integrating several subjects to different programs, aimed at developing the students' entrepreneurial mind and attributes of entrepreneurship. (Malolos, 2017)

The economic growth of a country depends on the economic activities of its entrepreneurs, entrepreneurs that all begin as young individuals who got what it takes to transform almost anything into an opportunity and had manifested entrepreneurship skills even while they were still students. But to adapt to changing circumstances, honing these skills becomes imperative not only for parents but most especially to the education system.

COVID-19 in the Philippines substantially tore down the country's economy. Asian Development Bank (2021) reported that the Philippines' gross domestic product was negative in 1999 (-9.6%). Nevertheless, the Philippines' economy has started to recover with a 5.6% year-on-year expansion in 2021 (World Bank, 2021). This crisis even opened the eyes and minds of every Filipino to look for other sources of income other than their regular jobs. During that time many lost their jobs and stayed at home. Every citizen thought about their income to get out of everyday life. Although there are aids from the government, it is not enough. So, with the help of social media, people had the opportunity to have a job and many jobs were created. This is one of the reasons why people learn how to run or manage a business. Because of this, it is necessary to learn the right way of doing business and the things that an entrepreneur must have. All this will be learned in school.

The importance for entrepreneurs to have the needed skills should be done while the students are still studying. But for the students' entrepreneurial skills to be beneficial, Kucel, et.al (2016) stressed the significance of adapting a stronger correlation

Learning Activity Worksheet and the Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies of Grade 10- Student in Technology and Livelihood Education

between the need for entrepreneurial skills training in higher education institutions and the policies that promote innovation at the micro and macro levels in countries' economies.

Mitchelmore and Rowley (2010) defined entrepreneurial competence as a concept that has many faces and applications. Further, the terms "skills", "expertise", "acumen" and "competency" are all interrelated and are sometimes used interchangeably in the literature (Smith and Morse, 2005 in Mitchelmore and Rowley, 2010). Entrepreneurs must have certain entrepreneurial competencies or skills to become successful.

Technology and Livelihood Education as one of the subjects offered to secondary students in the Philippines which taught diverse skills promote entrepreneurship education that would develop the personal entrepreneurial competency of the students. With the growing importance of globalization, students must be competitive by enhancing their personal entrepreneurial competencies. As part of the course, Grades 9 through 10 will concentrate on Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies wherein the learners will learn how to be an entrepreneur. Through this topic, students will then realize what will be their interest when they get into college.

One of the most important components of a business program is the entrepreneurial competency that needs to be explained to the students because future entrepreneurs will be among these students. Institutions of higher learning play a vital part in developing and disseminating this competency. After all, kids receive their education and training in the classroom. Future business owners are expected to learn the skills necessary for their upcoming ventures in school. Students equip themselves to become effective practicing entrepreneurs through formal schooling.

The researcher observed that the students particularly Grade 10 acquired weak points at some of the important personal entrepreneurial competencies as shown in the reported results of the evaluation of self-rating assessment for individual Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies (PECs). Among the behavioral indicators covered in the PECs, Information Seeking, Systematic Planning and Monitoring, and Persuasion and Networking received the lowest score. Understanding the results of this self-assessment tool greatly help in the detection and analysis of strong and weak points which are useful in strengthening the entrepreneurial potential.

To fill in this gap, the researcher's primary interest is to find the kind of learning resource that would help the learners to fully understand their lesson about Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies (PECs). The researcher uses her determination to develop worksheets to meet the needs and develop the competencies of the students. It will also help them in preparation for their Senior High School since the majority of these students would like to enroll in Technology – Vocational Livelihood Track which also focuses on these entrepreneurial competencies.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study aimed to determine the impact of the Learning Activity Worksheet in TLE and the Personal Entrepreneurial Competency and Skills in Grade -10 students.

1. What is the student perception on the extent of Learning Activity Worksheet in terms of:
 - 1.1 Time Frame;
 - 1.2 Content;
 - 1.3 Instruction; and
 - 1.4 Assessment
2. What is the mean pretest and posttest scores of the respondents before and after the utilization of Learning Activity Worksheet?
3. How do learners apply personal entrepreneurial skills in TLE 10 in terms of:
 - 3.1 Achievement Cluster;
 - 3.2 Planning Cluster; and
 - 3.3 Power Cluster?
4. Is there significant difference between mean pretest and posttest scores of the respondents before and after the utilization of Learning Activity Worksheet?

LITERATURE REVIEW

The various expert opinions and research papers relevant to the current investigation are presented in this chapter. The researcher has reviewed journals, books, and previous theses that they felt were crucial for readers to understand the essence of this investigation. These academic works are cited in the hopes that they will support the validity of the current study.

Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies

In today's economy, entrepreneurship is essential since it encourages not only innovation but also the growth of the economy and country. Small business development and enterprise expansion are viewed as essential to the advancement of the economy. The development of pertinent information, abilities, and attitudes is only one aspect of entrepreneurship. It is instead intended to be a continuous learning environment and envisaged in terms of the continuous development of a person's core entrepreneurial skills (Oganisjana, 2012)

Learning Activity Worksheet and the Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies of Grade 10- Student in Technology and Livelihood Education

Meanwhile, Mitchelmore and Rowley (2013) described entrepreneurship as a process of action by anyone to establish his or her enterprise. Thus, entrepreneurship is a creative activity, it is said to be the ability to create and build something from absolutely nothing. Additionally, Ahamad, Halim, and Zainal (2010) described entrepreneurship as having fundamental qualities including features, reasons, self-images, social roles, and talents that lead to the growth and enhanced performance of the organization.

According to A. Bagheri and Z. A. L. Pihie (2011) indicates such personal entrepreneurial competencies as proactiveness, innovativeness and risk taking. Entrepreneurship education is the process of professional application of knowledge, attitude, skills, and competencies, it is not just teaching how to become independent business owner, it is much more – entrepreneurship education encompasses creating and nurturing a learning environment that promotes entrepreneurial traits and behaviors, such as becoming creative and independent thinker, risk-taker, assuming responsibility, and valuing diversity.

Moreover, A. Rauch and M. Frese (2007) defines 11 personality traits matched to entrepreneurship: self-efficacy, proactive personality, tenacity, need for achievement, stress tolerance, goal orientation, need for autonomy, innovativeness, endurance, flexibility and passion for work. G. Giancesini, S. Cubico, G. Favretto and J. Leitaó (2018) comparing three entrepreneurial models (EntreComp, The Great Eight, 13 Entrepreneurial Competencies model) summarize personality components as tenacity, creative problem solving/imaginativeness, self-efficacy, adaptability, motivation and perseverance, though just creativity/imaginativeness and adaptability is presented in all three models

Entrepreneurship is discovering novel business opportunities and organizing economic capital to exploit a new business opportunity or restructure an already operational one despite the uncertainty of making profits.

Entrepreneurship plays a vital aspect of contemporary economics as it makes accessible, not only transformation but job generation and also national opulence. The heightening and thriving of enterprises and small businesses are equivalent to economic elevation.

Furthermore, H. Neck, P. Greene and C. Brush (2014) state that entrepreneurship should have as a portfolio of practices, including practices of play, empathy, creation, experimentation and reflection, this way directing to experiential entrepreneurship education. In intermediate level students, qualities that are frequently associated with entrepreneurs can be influenced by entrepreneurship education and enterprise experience. students trained in greater self-esteem than a comparable group, higher success motivation, more personal autonomy, and overall greater entrepreneurial qualities. (Rasheed, 2001; Sabarre, 2013).

Meanwhile, According to Kyguolienė and Švipas (2019), The academic literature has actively discussed entrepreneurial competencies. They have concentrated on academic institutions and the recent uptick in start-ups, where entrepreneurial skills are highly valued.

Entrepreneurship training is the practice of using professionals. Knowing something is not the same as teaching someone how to do something. It takes considerably more entrepreneurship to be an independent business owner. Education includes developing and fostering a learning environment that encourages entrepreneurial qualities and behaviors, such as becoming an independent and creative thinker, taking risks, being responsible, and appreciating variety (Gautam, Singh, 2015).

On the other hand, Marlborough (2020), stated that students aspire to run personal businesses primarily for autonomy, financial security, and vocational flexibility.

Learning Activity Worksheets

The success of teaching and learning activities is greatly influenced by the instructional materials used. Worksheets are a type of printed educational resource that are created and regularly used by teachers to help students learn. By giving insightful feedback on the course objectives and allowing students to participate in active learning and learning-by-doing within and outside of the classroom, teachers may assist their students develop knowledge, skills, and values (Kaymakc, 2006).

Worksheets might be seen as a new phrase in relation to Turkey and Turkish educational literature. Indeed, worksheets were utilized in the classroom up until the 1990s, but they were not known by that name. They were known as exercise journals, tests, sketches, etc. (In Turkish, "temrin defterleri"). Scholars tended to investigate and disseminate modern educational technology and resources to the public after the policies of educational reorganization in Turkey in the 1990s.

The policy under DepEd Order No. 18 series of 2020, aims to establish the guidelines that will enable the Department of Education (DepEd) to provide learning resources and implement the Basic Education - Learning Continuity Plan (BE - LCP) to ensure that learning opportunities should be provided to the learners in a safe manner, using various learning delivery methods. Learning Activity Sheets were included in SLMs and are used to evaluate the learners' level of knowledge during the course (D.O. #18. S. 2020)

Student worksheets, according to Atasoy (Taslidere, 2013), are a teaching tool that let students develop their own knowledge and can inspire students to take part in learning activities in the classroom. The worksheet for students serves as a guide for practicum activities, among other things. A strategy for employing student worksheets is student worksheet inquiry, according to Johnstone and Shavaili (Majid, 2014), where the observation has not been chosen by the teacher so that the students' observations can vary.

Learning Activity Worksheet and the Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies of Grade 10- Student in Technology and Livelihood Education

The worksheet, meantime, was selected as a medium because it will assist the lecturer in managing the material, encourage students to actively seek for the information or material they need, and offer opportunities of putting into practice academic knowledge. This worksheet is a group study assignment that asks students to take down whatever notes they may have made before to class, talk about the content, and work out related puzzles as a reflective exercise.

According to (Pascarella & Terenzini 2005; Dumford & Miller, 2018). Teachers should also provide clear instructions, communicate to the students the learning goals, inform students of expectations, inform students on how to meet requirements, provide feedback, explain content to enhance students' understanding of concepts, organize learning activities to scaffold materials, create learning opportunities to demonstrate and reflect on learning, and provide constructive feedback in lessons. Teachers must also monitor children's progress and provide constructive feedback inside and outside the classroom throughout Home Based Learning (HBL)

However, the CTL (contextual Teaching and Learning) approach is a way to present learning material by exposing problems related to daily life that must be resolved by students to achieve educational goals (Dewi & Primayana, 2019). By applying context in learning, students can communicate and share ideas, as well as experience it themselves and work together to solve problems (Hasruddin et al., 2015). In addition, Situmorang (2013) also explains that a good textbook must be able to motivate learners by utilizing interesting things such as pictures, illustrations, examples of questions (cases), have sufficient material to support teaching, and can be used to support problem solving activities.

Students' worksheets will provide benefits for teachers and students. Teachers will have teaching materials that are ready to use, while students will get an independent learning experience and will learn to understand the written assignments contained in the students' worksheet (Depdiknas, 2007).

According to Piaget's Cognitive Development Theory, kids between the ages of 12 and 15 have not fully developed their ability to reason abstractly. Concrete items must still be present during the learning process. Nevertheless, the introduction of semicircular items. However, students have started to apply thinking strategies that can help them comprehend and resolve issues at this junior high school level.

The teaching and learning processes need to be changed significantly in order to improve the quality of physics education (Wirtha & Rapi, 2008). From the theory supporting the learning model, it is clear how the guided inquiry learning model is used in the practical tasks in the student worksheet. The guided inquiry model is founded on constructivism philosophy, in which students create their own knowledge by engaging directly with an item or issue. According to Koksai and Berberoglu (2014), inquiry learning is implemented and has a good impact on students' cognitive and affective skills. Furthermore, guided inquiry models can help students develop a scientific mindset and scientific process abilities (Karim, Zainuddin, & Mastuang, 2016)

According to Schramm et al. (2018), students could gain from instruction that directly addresses these processes. Communication is precise, logical, and appropriate for the topic and goals. Both the teacher's resources and the student's materials clearly clarify the tasks. A wide range of skills and academic levels can access the information. The instructional strategy incorporates exercises that promote student participation and self-expression.

Meanwhile, Lee (2014), stated that using worksheets for a variety of objectives (in addition to textbooks and adding information for specific grade levels) may be helpful for academic success. Because worksheets instruct students on what to do, involve them in the learning process, and allow them to acquire information by forcing them to think. It also has a special significance because it is a resource that teachers and students can prepare independently according to the circumstances. Because of this, teachers can create worksheets that are appropriate for students' levels by anticipating what they would appreciate and how they will learn best (Isik & Ozdemir, 2014). The key at this point is to successfully transfer the knowledge to the student by connecting it to everyday experiences. This emphasizes the workbooks' layout.

Worksheets, in the opinion of Aydogdu and Keserciolu, are crucial tools for helping students organize their information, including the steps they must take to complete a task, and they guarantee that the entire class is participating at once. Because they have the freedom to choose how and where to employ the given assignments, Mortensen and Smartt describe worksheets as an approach that enables individuals to direct their own learning.

With their simplicity in mathematics instruction, ability to be produced in accordance with the subject matter, and ability to prevent lessons from becoming repetitive, worksheets are a component of modern teaching methods according to Demirel (2004).

Student worksheets, according to Atasoy (Taslidere, 2013), are instructional materials that let students develop their own knowledge and can motivate students to take part in classroom learning activities.

Meanwhile, Rahayu et al. (2018) claimed that the created student worksheet may be used to enhance thinking abilities through an integrated skills process that entails parts generating issues, developing hypotheses, finding variables, and defining operational definitions. Additionally, worksheets for students can help with social interactions including teamwork, listening to and considering the perspectives of peers, data collection, discussion of work practices, and information sharing.

Worksheets are viewed as an excellent teaching tool because they give students step-by-step instructions on how to methodically explore their notions (Proctor et al., 1997). To provide adequate communication between students and worksheets,

Learning Activity Worksheet and the Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies of Grade 10- Student in Technology and Livelihood Education

worksheets are composed of well-arranged assignments and questions. It is intended that students would develop their own solutions through discussions with professors and their peers. After the majority of pupils subscribe to others through dialogues, it is thought that they develop their own accurate conceptions. Instead of elaborating on the subject, teachers ask questions in this method to encourage pupils to develop their own ideas. Worksheets have a distinct statement of objectives, guidelines, required materials, and activities for individuals or groups, while according to Kwakman (2003), learning is seen as a proactive, beneficial, collaborative, and situation-specific activity. This activity aims to give students a productive learning experience that will help them expand their own knowledge and fully comprehend the subject matter being covered.

Furthermore, Authentic problem-based student worksheets and scientific approaches will facilitate students' learning to think critically and creatively to create enthusiasm, optimism, and self-confidence through "let's try, think big, let's work, and let's experiment" (Suryawati, 2017).

In improving the quality of physics learning, a distinctive change is needed in teaching and learning activities (Wirtha & Rapi, 2008). The use of guided inquiry learning model in practicum activities in the student worksheet can be seen from the theory underlying the learning model. The guided inquiry model is based on constructivism theory where students build their own knowledge through real-life experiences of an object or problem. The implementation of inquiry learning positively affects students' cognitive and affective abilities (Koksal & Berberoglu, 2014). In addition, the guided inquiry model is also able to train students' scientific attitude and students' scientific process skills (Karim, Zainuddin, & Mastuang, 2016).

METHODOLOGY

The study employed the one group pre-test post- test design as it aimed to accurately and systematically describe and identify characteristics, frequencies, trends, and categories of a population, situation or phenomenon. This design was appropriate since it determined and explained the data gathered from the participants' perception towards using a Learning activity worksheet.

With the features of descriptive research, data was gathered through questionnaire. The survey questionnaire was answered according to the priority of concern of the respondents by using a predetermined set of questions with predefined ranges of answers so as to avoid any conflicting series of response. Through the use of statistical treatment of data, appropriate conclusion and recommendation based on the findings were generated to give light to the objectives of the study. Hence, the researcher deemed that descriptive research design was the best to materialize this research work most effectively.

This research was conducted at Callejon National High School, Barangay Callejon, San Antonio, Province of Quezon during the 2022-2023 school year. The school has four sections of students in grade 10. The researcher used three sections where she was the Technology and Livelihood Education teacher. The three sections are composed of 106 students.

This research utilized purposive sampling. It is also known as judgment, selective or subjective sampling. It is a sampling technique in which a researcher relies on her own judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in the study. Purposive sampling methods may prove to be effective when only limited numbers of people can serve as primary data sources due to the nature of research design and aims and objectives. However, the respondents were all Grade 10 Students of Callejon National High School at Callejon San Antonio, Quezon.

In this study, the researcher carried out an investigation by utilizing a learning activity worksheet that was specifically designed to incorporate personal and entrepreneurial competencies. The purpose of incorporating these competencies within the worksheet was to ensure that the students participating in the study gained a comprehensive understanding of entrepreneurship. The learning activity worksheet served as a practical tool for the students, presenting them with a range of activities and exercises that aimed to develop their personal and entrepreneurial skills. By engaging with the worksheet, the students were exposed to various concepts, theories, and practical aspects related to entrepreneurship. The inclusion of personal competencies within the worksheet aimed to foster the development of qualities such as self-awareness, self-confidence, adaptability, and critical thinking. These competencies played a crucial role in preparing the students to face the challenges and uncertainties associated with entrepreneurship.

Furthermore, the worksheet also incorporated entrepreneurial competencies, which encompassed a diverse set of skills and knowledge necessary for entrepreneurial success. These competencies covered areas such as opportunity identification, business planning, marketing, financial management, and decision-making. By integrating these competencies into the learning activities, the researcher ensured that the students acquired a solid foundation in entrepreneurship. Through the utilization of the learning activity worksheet that incorporated personal and entrepreneurial competencies, the researcher aimed to equip the students with the essential knowledge and skills required to embark on entrepreneurial endeavors. The worksheet served as a comprehensive tool for facilitating the students' understanding of entrepreneurship, enabling them to develop the necessary competencies for success in the field.

Due to the fact that Callejon National High School offers the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) track with a specialization in Home Economics, it becomes essential for students enrolled in this program to acquire the aforementioned ideals.

Learning Activity Worksheet and the Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies of Grade 10- Student in Technology and Livelihood Education

This is primarily because these ideals play a crucial role in preparing them for future employment opportunities both locally and abroad, specifically within the business and work industries.

The learning activity worksheet designed for this study is structured into two distinct modules, intended to be completed over a span of 15 days. Each module comprises various components, including objectives, topics, activities, and assessments.

The objectives section outlines the specific goals and learning outcomes that the students are expected to achieve by engaging with the worksheet. These objectives serve as a guide for both the students and the researchers, ensuring that the activities and topics covered align with the intended educational outcomes. The topics covered in the worksheet encompass a wide range of relevant subject matter related to the study's focus. These topics are carefully selected to provide the students with a comprehensive understanding of the subject, promoting their knowledge and skill development in the specific area being explored.

The activities included within the worksheet serve as interactive exercises and tasks designed to engage the students actively in the learning process. These activities are structured to encourage critical thinking, problem-solving, collaboration, and creativity. By actively participating in these activities, students can apply the theoretical concepts they have learned and gain practical experience.

The researcher designed and implemented the necessary pre-processing for the analysis. She requested permission to conduct the study from the school administration in a letter that outlined its goals; when she received a positive response, she approved, and the researcher set to work gathering the data she would need to compile his report.

The study utilized research instruments namely, learning activity worksheet that is self-made, pretest and post-tests, survey questionnaire, that were created and validated as first procedure. The items given to the pretest are from the two lessons about Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies that are distributed equally across the pretest and post-test that were used. The post-test utilized was distributed at random.

Adopted and modified survey questionnaire also designed to determine the interest of the students on becoming an entrepreneur. As a guide in evaluation, they were given a written validation tool. The researcher took into account feedback, advice, and recommendations for enhancing and updating the teaching resource. After revision and essential refinement, the instrument was validated with assistance from peers, highly qualified teachers, and specialists.

Respondents were given an orientation on the purposes of the study. Upon approval, the questionnaire was personally distributed to the participants to answer the questions raised by them.

Likewise, confidentiality of the responses was secured. Respondents were given enough time to answer the questionnaire. Upon retrieval, results were tallied, analysed and interpreted using appropriate statistical tools.

The researcher used an adapted and modified survey questionnaire. She sought the assistance of the experts and panel in determining the accuracy of its content. It was presented to the research adviser for final approval after a series modifications and improvements. The questionnaires were distributed to the respondents once they had been approved.

Frequency, Percentage was used to determine the respondents' improvement before and after the implementation of Learning Activity Worksheet.

To determine student perception on the extent of Learning Activity Worksheet in terms of; frame, content, instruction and assessment mean and standard deviation were used. To examine the mean pre-test and post test scores of the before and after the utilization of Learning Activity Worksheet mean and standard deviation were used. To determine learners' application on personal entrepreneurial skills in TLE 10 in terms of; Achievement Cluster, Planning Cluster and Power Cluster mean and standard deviation were used.

To analyze the significant difference between mean pretest and posttest scores of the respondents before and after the utilization of Learning Activity Worksheet t-test was used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 show respondents perceived to the extent of the learning activity worksheet as to Time frame. Based from the give table, it is indicated that respondents described the learning activity worksheet in the time frame, the indicator no.5 got the highest mean of 3.43 (SD=0.50) and interpret as "Agree". This could mean the given time in doing activity is well distributed accomplish simple task. Moreover, indicator no.2 got lowest from all indicators and garnered a weighted mean of 3.25 (SD= 0.50) with verbal interpretation of "Agree". This revealed that the given time suits the expected period to answer the activity or worksheets. Furthermore, the overall result showed that in terms of doing activity worksheet as to time frame was seems fully effective supported by the overall weighted mean of 3.36, (SD=0.36)

Learning Activity Worksheet and the Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies of Grade 10- Student in Technology and Livelihood Education

Table 1
Perception of the Respondents on Learning Activity Worksheet in terms of Time Frame

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. Allocated time for each activity is well distributed.	3.35	0.48	<i>Great Extent</i>
2. The given time suits the estimated time to answer the worksheets.	3.25	0.50	<i>Great Extent</i>
3. The projected time to accomplished falls under the given period.	3.35	0.48	<i>Great Extent</i>
4. Time spent for the activity is suited to my ability	3.42	0.50	<i>Great Extent</i>
5. Time given to the activity is well divided to manage simple task.	3.43	0.50	<i>Great Extent</i>
Overall	3.36	0.31	<i>Great Extent</i>

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Strongly Agree/Very great extent) 2.50-3.49 (Agree/ Great Extent) 1.50-2.49 (Disagree/ Some Extent) 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree/ Not at All)

On average, the participants agreed (mean= 3.43) that the content of the activities is arranged from simple to challenging. The standard deviation of 0.50 indicates moderates’ variability in responses, but overall, there is agreement regarding this statement.

Overall, considering all the statements, the participants’ average agreement level was 3.44 which falls within the “Agree/ Great extent ” category. This suggests that, on average, the participants agreed with the statements related to the extent of learning activity content.

According to Schramm et al. (2018), students could gain from instruction that directly addresses these processes. Communication is precise, logical, and appropriate for the topic and goals. Both the teacher's resources and the student's materials clearly clarify the tasks. A wide range of skills and academic levels can access the information. The instructional strategy incorporates exercises that promote student participation and self-expression.

According to Delos Reyes and Caballes (2021), the activity design process entails meticulously preparing learning experiences to achieve those two objectives. Using a proven design strategy is the first step in creating successful, high-quality learning activities. The learning objectives for each activity must be examined both during and after the activity to ensure that the required degree of comprehension was supplied.

Table 2
Perception of Respondent on Learning Activity Worksheet in terms of Content/

Statement	Mean	SD	VI
1. The content of the activities are arranged from simple to challenging.	3.43	0.50	<i>Great extent</i>
2. The activities are consistent with the objectives.	3.40	0.51	<i>Great extent</i>
3. The lessons contained in the worksheet serve as a guide in developing my Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies.	3.50	0.50	<i>Very great extent</i>
4. The worksheet is properly laid out.	3.33	0.47	<i>Great extent</i>
5. Questions and tasks are clearly labeled with numbers and letters.	3.55	0.50	<i>Very great extent</i>
Overall	3.44	0.29	<i>Great Extent</i>

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Strongly Agree/Very Great Extent) 2.50-3.49 (Agree /Great Extent) 1.50-2.49 (Disagree/ Some Extent) 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree/ Not at All)

Learning Activity Worksheet and the Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies of Grade 10- Student in Technology and Livelihood Education

Table 3 shows the perception on learning Activity Worksheet in terms of Instruction

Overall, considering all the statements, the participants average agreement level was 3.52, which falls within the strongly Agree” category. This suggests that on average, the participants strongly agreed. (mean=3.48) that the worksheet instructions lead learners into clear visualization of the given task. The standard deviation 0.50 indicates moderate variability in responses, but overall, there is agreement regarding this statement.

According to the authors Richardson, J. C., and Swan, K. (2003), exercises that require students to interact with the material can include listening to and watching a live or recorded lecture, interacting with a written or visual text, interacting with multimedia, or a mix of these.

Table 3. |
Perception of Respondents on Learning Activity Worksheet in terms of Instruction

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
The worksheet instructions...			
1. are well -explained and concise.	3.47	0.50	Great extent
2. are clearly written.	3.60	0.49	Very great Extent
3. are simple and self-guided.	3.54	0.50	Very great extent
4. guide the learners to easily accomplish the given task.	3.48	0.50	Great Extent
5. lead learners into clear visualization of the given task.	3.48	0.50	Great extent
Overall	3.52	0.32	Very great extent

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Strongly Agree/ Very great extent) 2.50-3.49 (Agree/Great extent) 1.50-2.49 (Disagree/Some extent) 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree/ Not at all)

Based on the data provided in Table 4, we have set of statements related to the extent of learning activity assessment and their respective mean, standard deviation (SD), and the participants’ agreement level.

Overall, considering all statements, the participants’ average agreement level was 3.38, which falls within the agree category. This suggest that, on average, the participants agreed with the statements related to the extent of learning activity assessment.

According to Wasserman, et al (2007), adhering to an explicit design approach is the first step in producing successful, high-quality learning experiences. To make sure that each activity produced the required degree of comprehension, student learning must be assessed both during and after the activity.

Table 4.
Perception of Respondent on Learning Activity Worksheet in terms of / Assessment

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. The tools used in assessment achieved the level of mastery expected.	3.40	0.49	Great extent
2. Assessments are gauge with targeted competency / objective.	3.26	0.44	Great extent
3. The art of questioning in the assessment is crafted	3.39	0.49	Great extent
4. The questions are anchored with the domain of learning.	3.40	0.49	Great extent
5. The tools used in the assessment comprises different forms of questions	3.48	0.50	Great extent
Overall	3.38	0.31	Great extent

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Strongly Agree/Very great extent) 2.50-3.49 (Agree/Great extent) 1.50-2.49 (Disagree/Some Extent) 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree Not at all)

Learning Activity Worksheet and the Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies of Grade 10- Student in Technology and Livelihood Education

The data in table 5 provides information about the result of the mean pretest and posttest scores before and after the utilization of the Learning Activity Worksheet. It shows that students only received a mean average of 11.51 interpreted as Developing during the pretest. The students are not yet exposed in the material during the pretest.

Overall, this data suggests that there has been an improvement from the pretest to the post test, as indicated by the higher average score on the posttest.

Table 5
Respondent Mean Pretest and Posttest Scores

Tests	Mean	SD	VI
Pretest	11.51	8.19	<i>Developing</i>
Posttest	19.11	10.22	<i>Proficient</i>
Overall			

Legend: 30.00-24.01 (*Advanced*); 24.00-18.01 (*Proficient*); 18.00-12.01 (*Approaching Proficiency*); 12.00-6.01 (*Developing*); 6.00-0.00 (*Beginning*)

The table 6 shows the respondents perception for Personal entrepreneurial competency as to Achievement cluster it reveals that all the indicators are on average (usually level) with mean 3.13 and SD of 0.39.

It implies that the respondents are value every opportunity to do the things that are important, and they don't give up on trials.

Table 6
Personal Entrepreneurial Skills as to Achievement Cluster

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. Spend a lot of time trying to find a solution when I am faced with a difficult problem.	3.24	0.68	<u><i>Usually</i></u>
2. Complete my work on time	3.21	0.66	<u><i>Usually</i></u>
3. Do things that need to be done before being asked by others.	3.10	0.70	<u><i>Usually</i></u>
4. Like challenges and new opportunities.	3.11	0.80	<u><i>Usually</i></u>
5. Feel bothered when my time is wasted.	3.14	0.86	<u><i>Usually</i></u>
6. Feel confident that I will succeed when trying something challenging	3.27	0.75	<u><i>Usually</i></u>
7. Prefer activities that I know well and with which I am comfortable.	3.32	0.75	<u><i>Usually</i></u>
8. Feel confident that I will succeed at whatever I try to do.	3.08	0.82	<u><i>Usually</i></u>
9. Try things that are very new and different from what I have done.	3.03	0.72	<u><i>Usually</i></u>
10. Do things that other considered risky.	2.83	0.83	<u><i>Usually</i></u>
Overall	3.13	0.39	<u><i>Usually</i></u>

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (*Always*); 2.50-3.49 (*Usually*); 1.50-2.49 (*Rarely*); 1.00-1.49 (*Never*)

Table 7 presents data on Personal Entrepreneurial skills related to the Planning Cluster. Each statement is accompanied by its mean, standard deviation (SD), and Verbal Interpretation (VI) indicating the frequency at which respondents exhibit the mentioned behavior.

Overall, across all the statements, the respondents, on average, demonstrate personal entrepreneurial skills in the Planning Cluster at a "usually" level (mean=3.25, SD= 040). It implies that the respondents are somewhat patient and If they are given the opportunity to be given a job, they can do it, and they will be more prosperous if they are guided or taught.

Learning Activity Worksheet and the Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies of Grade 10- Student in Technology and Livelihood Education

Li (2009)'s research proved that entrepreneurs typically have compared to non-entrepreneurs, a higher level of entrepreneurial competencies, and both can be grouped according to their level of competency. These results imply that business owners may be better equipped than non-business owners in in terms of ability.

Table 7
Personal Entrepreneurial Skills as to Planning Cluster

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. Gather a great deal of information when starting a new task.	3.17	0.65	<u>Usually</u>
2. Plan a large project by breaking down into smaller task.	2.90	0.68	<u>Usually</u>
3. Try several ways to overcome things that get in the way of reaching my goals.	3.35	0.68	<u>Usually</u>
4. Think about the advantages and disadvantages of different way of accomplishing things.	3.44	0.66	<u>Usually</u>
5. Have a very clear plan for my life.	3.37	0.72	<u>Usually</u>
6. Think of solutions that will help reach my goals.	3.46	0.62	<u>Usually</u>
7. Find ways to complete task faster at work and at home.	3.18	0.70	<u>Usually</u>
8. Go to several different sources to get information for tasks or projects.	3.10	0.68	<u>Usually</u>
9. Feel that the more specific I can be about what I want out of life, the more chances I have to succeed.	3.14	0.72	<u>Usually</u>
10. Look for things that need to be done.	3.36	0.71	<u>Usually</u>
Overall	3.25	0.40	<u>Usually</u>

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Always) 2.50-3.49 (Usually) 1.50-2.49 (Rarely) 1.00-1.49 (Never)

Table 8 presents data on Personal Entrepreneurial Skills in relation to the Power Cluster

Each statement is accompanied by its mean, standard deviation (SD), and Variance (VI) Variance Index, indicating the frequency at which respondents exhibit the mentioned behavior.

Overall, across all statements, the respondents, on average, exhibit personal entrepreneurial skills in the Power Cluster at a “usually” level (mean=3.10, SD=0.42)

Learning Activity Worksheet and the Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies of Grade 10- Student in Technology and Livelihood Education

Table 8. Personal Entrepreneurial Skills as to Power Cluster

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. can get others to support my recommendations.	3.15	0.64	<u>Usually</u>
2. can get important people to help me accomplish my goals.	3.27	0.67	<u>Usually</u>
3. stick to my decisions even if others disagree strongly with me.	2.96	0.74	<u>Usually</u>
4. can get people who have strong opinions or ideas to change their minds.	3.08	0.66	<u>Usually</u>
5. deal with problems as they arise, rather spend time trying to anticipate them.	3.03	0.80	<u>Usually</u>
6. make a special effort to make sure that when I am doing a job for someone that person is satisfied with my work.	3.49	0.59	<u>Usually</u>
7. feel resentful when I don't get my way.	2.94	0.69	<u>Usually</u>
8. prefer situations in which I can control the outcomes as much as possible.	3.20	0.74	<u>Usually</u>
9. try several times to get <u>people</u> to do what I would like them to do.	2.94	0.73	<u>Usually</u>
10. believe that my work is always better than that of other people I work with.	2.94	0.97	<u>Usually</u>
Overall	3.10	0.42	<u>Usually</u>

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Always) 2.50-3.49 (Usually) 1.50-2.49 (Rarely) 1.00-1.49 (Never)

Table 9 presents the results of a test conducted to determine the difference between pretest and posttest scores. Here is the interpretation of the data.

According to the provided table, there is a significant difference between the student respondents' pretest and posttest performance before and after using the learning activity worksheet, with a significance value of .000, which is less than 0.05. It suggests that after using a learning exercise worksheet, their learning has significantly improved.

The note at the bottom table states that a significant difference exists between the pretest and posttest scores. This suggests that there was a meaningful change or improvement in the scores from the pretest to the posttest.

Table 9
Difference Between the Pretest and Posttest Scores

Tests	Mean	SD	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Pretest	11.51	8.19	6.435	105	.000
Posttest	19.11	10.22			

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, this conclusion was drawn:

1. The hypothesis is not sustained.
2. The null hypothesis stating “there is no significant relationship in student’s perception on the use of Learning Activity Worksheet and their personal entrepreneurial skills” is accepted.

Learning Activity Worksheet and the Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies of Grade 10- Student in Technology and Livelihood Education

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results and conclusions posted in the study, the following recommendations are hereby formulated:

1. Through the findings of the study, administrators may understand the condition of the students and how they can craft their own Home-Based Learning Activities in TLE for Personal Entrepreneurial Competency and Skills.
2. The findings of the study may give insights to teachers to identify the activities that learners can easily follow or understand that they may create for the students based on the needed competency to have a good performance even though face-to-face classes are not possible and result in high MPS on the subject.
3. Future researchers may as well consider the use of the study and incorporate them into their studies to further validate the findings of the study.

REFERENCES

- 1) An Mansor, NH Zabarani , KA Jamaludin , MY Mohd Nor , BS Alias Home Based Learning (HBL) teacher readiness scale: Instrument development and demographic analysis
- 2) CC Klein, M Rastogi , ML Barnett Children and Youth Service Review ,(2021)
- 3) D Elmuti, G Khoury, the Oman journal of Entrepreneurship (2012) reseach gate .
- 4) Neufeld, Gordon, & Mate, Gabor (2004) Hold on to your Kids: Why Parents need to matter more than peers. New York, NY: Ballentine Books
- 5) Home-School- Researcher attachment- theory-and home-based-education. Retrieved from [http:// www.nheri.org](http://www.nheri.org)
- 6) The Reality of Home – Based Learning During Covid-19: Roles of Parents, Teachers, and School Administration in Promoting Self-Directed Learning; Volume5, Issue S2 (2020), pp 85-92 Journal of School Administration Research and Development ISSN: 2470-8496 Print/ ISSN: 2470-850X
- 7) Uku Lillevale 1 and Marge Task 1,2 1 Competence Models as a Tool for Conceptualizing the Systematic Process of Entrepreneurship Competence Development Uku Lillevale 1 and Marge Task 1,2 1 University of Tartu, Ulikooli 18,50090 Tartu,Estonia 2 Estonian Business School, Lauteri 3, 10114 Tallinn, Estonia
- 8) Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies of the Business Students of Kalinga State University: A Basis for Enhancement of Teaching Strategies and development Program Structure, Karen Razelle M. Duyan
- 9) D Elmuli, G Khoury, O Omran- *Does Entrepreneurship education have role in developing entrepreneurial*
- 10) MLV Alusen ; Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies of LPU Laguna BSBA graduating *Skills and venture's effectiveness?* Journal of Entrepreneurship, 2012
- 11) Students : Basis for Curriculum Enhancement- *LPU laguna Journal of Multidisciplinary Research* 2016-
- 12) Jean Ho and Lee Yong Tay ISEA. Volume 48, Number 2, 2020 1 49 Ensuring Learning Continues During Pandemic Oct. 25, 2022
- 13) Regular Article Published 13 April 2021 Implementation of Online Home-Based Learning And Students' Engagement During the Covid- 19 Pandemic : A Case Study of Singapore Mathematics Teachers
- 14) Lee Yong Tay, Shu -Shing Lee & Kalaivani Ramachandran *The Asian- Pacific Education Researcher* volume 30, pages 299- 310 (2021)
- 15) Rona M. Idio , Dr. Henly F. Martirez Parental Involvement to the Learning Tasks on Learners Academic Performance in Technology a and Livelihood Education
- 16) LM – Cookery Grade 9
- 17) LM- Cookery Grade 10
- 18) Misbah, M., Dewantara, D., Hasan, S. M., & Annur, S. (2018). The development of student worksheet by using Guided Inquiry Learning Model to train student's scientific attitude. *Unnes Science Education Journal*, 7(1).
- 19) University of Muhammadiyah Malang, Jl. Raya Tlogomas 246, Malang 65144, Indonesia; University of Muhammadiyah Malang, Jl. Raya Tlogomas 246, Malang 65144, Indonesia
- 20) The effect of prompting question on students' worksheet -based on guided inquiry towards students' learning achievement and activity of class X MIA of MA Negeri 1 Makassar (study on electrolyte and nonelectrolyte solution)
- 21) Sudding, Taty Sulastry and Anugrah Alam Universitas Negeri Makassar, Jalan Dg. Tata Raya, Makassar 90224, Indonesia Ransom, M., & Manning, M. (2013). Teaching strategies: Worksheets, worksheets, worksheets. *Childhood Education*, 89(3), 188-190
- 22) İnan, C., & Erkus, S. (2017). The Effect of Mathematical Worksheets Based on Multiple Intelligences Theory on the Academic Achievement of the Students in the 4th Grade Primary School. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 5(8), 1372-1377.
- 23) Çelik, E., BAKI, G. O., & Ahmet, I. S. I. K. (2022). The Effect Of Cluster Teaching With Worksheets On Students'academic Achievement In Distance Education. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 23(3), 137-152

Learning Activity Worksheet and the Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies of Grade 10- Student in Technology and Livelihood Education

- 24) Chong, V. D., Salleh, S. M., & AiCheong, I. P. (2013). Using an activity worksheet to remediate students' alternative conceptions of metallic bonding. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 3(11), 39-52.
- 25) Misbah, M., Dewantara, D., Hasan, S. M., & Annur, S. (2018). The Development Of Student Worksheet by using Guided Inquiry Learning Model to train student's scientific attitude. *Unnes Science Education Journal*, 7(1).
- 26) Suryawati, E., Suzanti, F., Zulfarina, Z., Putriana, A. R., & Febrianti, L. (2020). The Implementation Of Local Environmental Problem-Based Learning Student Worksheets To Strengthen Environmental Literacy. *Jurnal Pendidikan IPA Indonesia*, 9(2), 169-178
- 27) Rizki, A., Khaldun, I., & Pada, A. U. T. (2021). Dedevlopment of Discovery Learning Student Worksheets to Improve Students' Critical Thinking Skills in Chemical Balance Materials. *Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan IPA*, 7(4), 707-711
- 28) Atasoy, S., Kucuk, M., & Akdeniz, A. R. (2011). Remedying science student teachers' misconceptions of force and motion using worksheets based on constructivist learning theory. *Energy Education Science and Technology Part B: Social and Educational Studies*, 3(4), 519-534.
- 29) Hidayat, D., Kohar, A. W., Prihartiwi, N. R., Mubarak, H., & Yohannes, A. (2021). Design of Learning Activities using Rigorous Mathematical Thinking (RMT) Approach in Application of Derivatives. *IJORER: International Journal of Recent Educational Research*, 2(1), 111-120.
- 30) Ma. Leonora V. Alusen Assistant Professor College of Business and Accountancy, Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies Of LPU- Laguna BSBA Graduating Students: Basis For Curriculum Enhancement
- 31) A M Fauziah¹, T Nurita¹ Activities of students in using worksheet based on Contextual Teaching and Learning 1Department of Science, Universitas Negeri Surabaya, Indonesia
- 32) Zukhrufurrohmah¹; Octavina Rizky Utami Putri¹ Learning activities using worksheet characterized by the Recognition Of Mathematical Symbols